

Fitting q-Gaussians onto Anatase TiO₂ Raman Bands

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Abstract: In previous studies, we used the Tsallis q-Gaussian functions for the analysis of Raman spectra, providing several successful examples. Here we apply q-Gaussians to anatase TiO₂ Raman spectra from literature, and from RRUFF and ROD databases. We will discuss, in particular, the Raman band about 515 cm⁻¹, and its decomposition in A_{1g} and B_{1g} modes.

Keywords: Tsallis q-Gaussian distribution, Gaussian distribution, Cauchy distribution, Lorentzian distribution, Raman spectroscopy, Anatase, TiO₂

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q-Gaussian Tsallis functions are probability distributions proper of the Tsallis statistics and based on a generalized form of the exponential function, characterized by a continuous parameter q in the range $1 < q < 3$ (Tsallis, 1988, 1995, Umarov et al., 2008, Hanel et al., 2009, Sparavigna, 2022). The q-Gaussian function is given as $f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2)$, where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a scale constant. In the exponent, $\beta = 1/(2\sigma^2)$, we used the variance σ . The q-exponential has expression: $exp_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$. For q equal to 2, the q-Gaussian is the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution (Naudts, 2009), and for q close to 1, we have the usual Gaussian form.

For q -parameter between 1 and 2, the shape of q-Gaussian function is intermediate between the Gaussian and the Lorentzian profile. This behavior turns q-Gaussians into functions suitable for the analysis of Raman spectra, where the spectral bands are characterized, in the same manner, by intermediate profiles between Lorentzian and Gaussian outlines (Kirillov, 2004). Besides these two functions, which remain the most popular for fitting Raman spectra, *linear combinations* (pseudo-Voigt distributions) or *convolutions* of them (Voigt distributions) are used too (Meier, 2005). The Voigtian function is essentially a Lorentzian height weighted by a Gaussian profile.

Of the reason for using Voigtian functions, and their pseudo-Voigtian approximations, we discussed in the previous work about q-Gaussians fitting onto graphite Raman bands ([ChemRxiv](#)). Shortly, the discussion was as follow. In spectroscopy, if the emission is broadened by radiation damping, the band profile is assumed as given by a Lorentzian model. The Lorentzian profile can be modified by different mechanisms. Among them we have the thermal broadening that introduces a convolution with a Gaussian function, resulting in a consequent Voigtian profile; alternatively, we can consider the convolution with a spectrophotometer Gaussian sensitivity function (Tatum, 2022). In any case, we have always a convolution of lines with instrumental function profiles. The “instrumentally induced distortion of the true band shape” is called as the “*instrument function*” by Seshadri and Jones, 1963, and the “*instrumental transfer function*” by Merlen et al., 2017. Consequently, the true spectral distribution, which is subjected to “distortions both in the *optical and recording parts* of the apparatus” (Rautian, 1958), is replaced by the observed measured distribution. Besides the models based on Voigtian convolution, other approaches exist (Kirillov, 2004), so

that the true radiation line can be assumed different from a Lorentzian function; moreover, the weight function can be different from a pure Gaussian function. Therefore, the measured distribution can be assumed different from the pure Voigtian function.

With its intermediate behavior, the q-Gaussian is suitable to describe convolution mechanisms in general. In Sparavigna, 2023, we have shown that the q-Gaussian is able of mimicking pseudo-Voigt, Voigt and Egelstaff-Schofield line shapes. Besides a detailed discussion of the decomposition in bands of Raman spectra for carbonaceous material, in Sparavigna, 2023, [link](#), we have shown several examples which demonstrate the q-Gaussians properly suitable for the Raman spectral data analysis. Here, we consider the q-exponential function for fitting onto the Raman spectrum of anatase, a natural occurrence of the titanium dioxide.

Why is anatase important? “Titanium oxide nanoparticles (TiO_2 , anatase) are the most explored photocatalytic nanoparticles, and they have extensive application within catalysis, self-cleaning, UV-shielding, optical filters, organic photovoltaic (OPV), organic and printed electronics, and many others”, as told by [particularmaterials.com](#). “Recently, a broad range of research efforts has been devoted to enhancing the optical and electrical properties of TiO_2 , resulting in improved photocatalytic activity” (Kang et al., 2019). In Kang and coworkers review, the “state-of-the-art modification strategies in optimizing the photocatalytic performance of TiO_2 ” are given.

In nature we can find the titanium dioxide in three crystalline modifications: rutile (tetragonal), anatase (tetragonal) and brookite (orthorhombic). In these lattices, each titanium ion is surrounded by a distorted oxygen octahedron (Ohsaka et al., 1978, and references therein). Here we consider, besides those from literature, the data coming from RRUFF collection (Lafuente et al., 2015), and from Raman Open Database, developed in the framework of project SOLSA H2020 (El Mendili et al., 2019). In the following plots, data are generally given in red and the best fits in green: q-Gaussian components are shown in blue and magenta colours. The misfit is also proposed in the lower part of the images. Data and best fits are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced points), for the x-axis, which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y-axis (intensity axis). Semi log plots are also proposed.

In Balachandran and Eror, 1982, we can find the Raman spectrum of anatase, “obtained by heating the glassy precursor to 450°C ”. The given frequencies of Raman bands are 147, 198, 320, 398, 448, 515, 640, and 796 cm^{-1} . Muzaffar Boda, 2018, explains that the Raman range $246\text{--}351\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to O–O covalent interactions. The modes at 144 and 197 cm^{-1} are due to Ti–Ti interaction in the unit cell. “Based on space group symmetry ... group theoretical analysis shows Raman active bands at 144, 197, 392, 515 and 633 cm^{-1} which corresponds to $E_g(1)$, $E_g(2)$, B_{1g} , A_{1g} and $E_g(3)$ modes of anatase phase, respectively. E_g bands arise mainly due to symmetric stretching vibration of O–Ti–O, B_{1g} band is due to symmetric bending vibration of O–Ti–O and A_{1g} mode is due to antisymmetric bending vibration of Ti–O–Ti in TiO_2 ” (Boda, 2018). For modes in TiO_2 nanotubes, see Boda and Shah, 2017.

RRUFF ID R060277 - Let us consider anatase Raman spectrum RRUFF ID 060277 <https://rruff.info/anatase/display=default/R060277>. As told by the web site, the sample was oriented and mounted on a pin, laser parallel to c^* (0 0 1) and fiducial mark perpendicular to laser is parallel to [1 1 0]. The sample was coming from Taftan, near Dalbandi, Baluchistan Province, Pakistan (Source: Herb Obodda 064, owner: RRUFF). “The identification of this mineral is confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction and chemical analysis” (RRUFF).

We start using depolarized processed data. About acquisition of polarized and depolarized Raman signals, see Kiefer, 2017: “If the laser is linearly polarized, the majority of the Raman signal will be polarized in the same way”, due to scattering events maintaining the polarization state. “A small fraction of the scattered light, however, will be polarized orthogonally with respect to the incident light. This is referred to as the depolarized signal”. The ratio of depolarized and polarized signals (depolarization ratio) is providing information about the symmetry of a vibrational mode (Kiefer, 2017).

From RRUFF file, we can identify peaks at 144, 198, 317, 398, 517, 639.5, 799 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 1: Processed data of RRUFF ID 060277 depolarized. On the right, the data with log scale y-axis (semi log scale). The semi log scale helps us to identify five ranges, named A, B, C, D and E, suitable to investigate the q -Gaussian fitting. The endpoints of frequency ranges are easily determined by their lowest intensities, evidenced by the semi log scale.

Fig. 2: The best fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R060277 depolarized Raman spectrum (red), range A (see Fig.1). Three q -Gaussians are used (values of the q -parameters are given in the figure). The misfit is proposed in the lower part of the plot. On the right, the same fit is shown with the log scale for y-axis (semi log scale). Data and q -Gaussians are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced points used in fitting), for the x-axis which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y-axis (intensity axis). The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=620$). In the semi log plot, on the right, we can see very well the mode at 198 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 3: The same as in the Fig.2, for RRUFF ID R060277 depolarized Raman spectrum (red), range B. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=620$). In the semi log plot, we can see very well the band at 317 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 4a: As before, RRUFF ID R060277 depolarized Raman spectrum (red), range C. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=448$). The value of this sum is about 9.0×10^{-3} . For fitting, here we used only one q -Gaussian. The plot is evidencing the asymmetry of the band.

Fig. 4b: The same as in the Fig.4a. Let us search for two components, the first having its centre on the left, the other on the right of the blue peak.

Fig. 4c: The same range as in the Fig.4a, in a fit with two components. The value of the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=448$) is 4.7×10^{-4} . We will further discuss the decomposition of this range. Let us anticipate that the fit here proposed has been obtained just guessing two components, without any further information (unconstrained guess). However, some constraints exist.

Fig. 5: RRUFF ID R060277 depolarized Raman spectrum (red), range D.

Fig. 6: RUFF ID R060277 depolarized Raman spectrum (red), range E.

From the figures given above, we can note a very good agreement. The five ranges have been fitted independently from each other (see Appendix A). In the case of the range C (Figure 4), we can see an asymmetric peak. We have resolved it into two bands. The same happens for the polarized component (see Appendix B). In any case, the range C is requiring a further discussion.

Discussion (first part) - Let us consider Ohsaka and coworkers' research on Raman spectrum of anatase (please consider that the figures given above are regarding the depolarized signal). Ohsaka and coworkers tell: "Spectra obtained for different polarizations are reproduced in [the Figures 2 and 3 of Ohsaka et al. article]". The researchers used the polarizability tensors as represented by Damen et al., 1966. "From Fig. 2, [of Ohsaka et al. article] the three Raman bands at 639, 197 and 144 cm^{-1} are definitely assigned to the E_g modes in accordance with the assignment by Beattie and Gilson" (Ohsaka et al., 1978, Beattie & Gilson, 1969). "The Raman band at 144 cm^{-1} is very intense and sharp. The frequency of this band in anatase, 144 cm^{-1} , is nearly equal to that of the B_{1g} mode in rutile (143 cm^{-1}) which is sharp but weak" (Ohsaka et al., 1978). "At room temperature the α_{xx} spectrum exhibits two peaks at 516 and 399 cm^{-1} besides the E_g mode at 144 cm^{-1} and three weak combination bands near 796, 695 and 320 cm^{-1} ." (Ohsaka et al., 1978).

In the Fig. 3 of Ohsaka and coworkers' research, we can see that the "516 cm^{-1} Raman band which occurs at room temperature is apparently split into two peaks centred at 519 and 513 cm^{-1} at low temperature (73 K). On the other hand, no Raman band which could be unambiguously assigned to the A_{1g} mode was observed in the α_{xx} spectrum at room temperature or at low temperatures. Since the A_{1g} mode is the Ti-O stretching type vibration one of the two bands at 519 and 513 cm^{-1} corresponds to the A_{1g} mode and consequently, the other to the B_{1g} mode. The 399 cm^{-1} band is assigned to one of the two B_{1g} modes" (Ohsaka et al., 1978). Regarding the Fig.3 in Ohsaka et al., the position of the peak at room temperature seems being at a value of 517 cm^{-1} , rather than 516 cm^{-1} .

In Giarola et al., 2010, we find at 512 cm^{-1} and 518 cm^{-1} the positions of A_{1g} and B_{1g} peaks, as given from experimental results (room temperature). In the article by Giarola et al., we can find how these two peaks have been determined by using different polarizations (see the detailed discussion in page 174305-4 of their article).

In the cartoon given above, we illustrated the insert in the Fig.3 of Giarola et al., 2010, approximately sketched. We can see two components with rather different weight. The positions are reported in the Table II of the given reference. The distance of the Raman shifts is of 6 cm^{-1} . The decomposition is different from the decomposition of the range about 517 cm^{-1} , according to the two q-Gaussians, given in the Figure 4c. In our decomposition, the distance of components' centres, at 515.5 and 524.5 cm^{-1} respectively, is of about 9 cm^{-1} . Of course, the sample is different. Giarola et al. investigated a natural crystal from Val d'Ossola, Italy. The instrumental set up was different.

Besides the depolarized data, the web page <https://ruff.info/anatase/display=default/R060277> is also providing data with three different directions of polarization of laser relative to fiducial mark: 0 ccw, 45 ccw and 90 ccw (see please the plot at this [link](#)). If we use R060277 polarized 0 ccw Raman spectrum processed data, we have two q-Gaussian components having $q=1.38$, centre at 516 cm^{-1} , and $q=1.68$ at 525.5 cm^{-1} (see Appendix B). For R060277 polarized 45 ccw Raman spectrum data processed, we have $q=1.34$, 516.5 cm^{-1} , $q=1.74$, 526.5 cm^{-1} . In the case R060277 polarized 90 ccw Raman spectrum data processed, we find $q=1.38$, 517.5 cm^{-1} , $q=1.67$, 526 cm^{-1} . The plots are like that given in the Fig.4c. Let us stress that these are unconstrained fits, obtained just guessing the existence of two components, without any further information.

Giarola et al. data – Let us consider the data in the Figure 3 of Giarola et al., 2010. We assume the positions of the centers of the two q-Gaussians as can be observed in the figure by Giarola et al. In the following Figure 7, the two q-Gaussians fitting onto these data is proposed.

Fig. 7: Giarola et al. Raman spectrum (red), as in the Fig.3 of their article. The fitting calculation (green), with the components' positions fixed as in the figure, is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=400$). The value of this sum is about 1.5×10^{-2} . The q-Gaussians are given in blue and magenta colours.

Ohsaka et al. data – As previously told, the Fig. 3 of Ohsaka and coworkers' research shows us the 516 cm^{-1} Raman band split into two peaks centered at 519 and 513 cm^{-1} at 73 K . Using two q-Gaussians, we have the following fit onto Ohsaka et al. data.

Fig.8: Two q -Gaussians fitting onto Ohsaka and coworkers data at 73 K. The fitting is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=560$. The value of this sum is about 1.5×10^{-2} .

To observe the difference between q -Gaussian fitting and Lorentzian fitting, let us compare for Ohsaka and coworkers' data.

Fig.9a: Two q -Gaussians fitting onto Ohsaka and coworkers' data, compared with two Lorentzian functions fitting. The value of the sum of deviations for Lorentzians is about 2.3×10^{-2} .

Of course, we can reduce the misfit by increasing the number of components. Using three q -Gaussians at $n=220, 257, 315$, the sum of the deviations squares is strongly reduced to value 2.7×10^{-3} . However, what could be the reason for the existence of a third components? The presence of defects?

Fig.9b: Three q -Gaussians fitting onto Ohsaka and coworkers data at 73 K. The fitting is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=560$. The value of this sum is about 2.7×10^{-3} .

Ohsaka et al. are also providing data at room temperature. Here the fitting with two q -gaussians.

Fig.10: Two q -Gaussians fitting onto Ohsaka and coworkers' data at room temperature. The fitting is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=560$. The value of this sum is about 2.5×10^{-2} . The best fit is determining the position of the centers of the two components, as given in the figure.

The positions of the components' centers are in rather agreement with data at low temperature.

Frank et al. data - In Frank et al., 2012, the researchers used six isotope-labelled samples of titanium dioxide and the Raman scattering was investigated at temperatures down to 5 K. Their impressive work is rich of experimental data regarding rutile and anatase. In their Figure 5, we can see the frequency range 450-550 cm^{-1} Raman spectra of three anatase samples, “in the region of $B_{1g}(2)$ and A_{1g} bands measured at 5 K. Dotted lines represent Lorentzian shapes of the two bands with the solid lines being their convolution. The experimental data points are plotted as circles” (Frank et al., 2012). The decomposition is showing a small peak on the left, lower Raman shift, and a large peak on the right, larger Raman shift with respect to the central position of the range; this is the same decomposition we can find in Giarola et al., 2010, and investigated previously.

If we assume the Figure 5 in the article by Frank et al., 2012, superimposing a grid on the plots, we can note misfits at the wings. To illustrate this fact, the plot in the upper part (A) of the Figure 11 is given. The plot is showing data of Ti^{18}O_2 Raman spectrum as in Frank et al. Note please the wings, which have quite different intensity values (strong asymmetry). It is impossible that the two Lorentzian functions, as proposed by Frank et al., can fit their data because these functions are symmetric and have wings with negligible intensity values.

Fig.11: Upper panel A is showing data from Frank et al., 2012, as given in their Fig.5. Lower panel B is showing the same data, after adjusting the baseline.

Let us use the data as in the Figure 11B, and fit two q-Gaussians, with centres at the same positions given by Frank and coworkers.

Fig.12: Two q -Gaussian fitting onto data Fig.11B. The fitting calculation, with components' positions fixed as in Frank and coworkers' work, is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=400$). The value of this sum is about 7.1×10^{-3} .

We can improve the fit by adding components.

Fig.13: To improve the fit, we can use three q -Gaussians. The value of the sum of squares of deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=400$) is about 7.8×10^{-4} .

Discussion (second part) – Let us return to RRUFF sample and use the same data that we used for the Figure 4a,b,c, and try to fit with an arrangement as in Frank et al., 2012, and Giarola et al., 2010.

Using the same positions of the centres of the components given by Giarola et al., that is 512 and 518 cm^{-1} , we have the following results for RRUFF R060277 depolarized.

Fig. 14: RRUFF ID R060277 depolarized Raman spectrum (red), range C. The fitting calculation, with the components' positions fixed as in the figure, is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=448$). The value of this sum is about 6×10^{-3} .

However, we can also consider the positions given by Ohsaka et al., that is 513 and 519 cm^{-1} , in the range about 516 cm^{-1} . We have observed before that RRUFF 060277 has the peak at 517 cm^{-1} . Let us shift the positions of components to 514 and 520 cm^{-1} , and fit onto the data.

Fig. 15: RRUFF ID R060277 depolarized Raman spectrum (red), range C, processed data. The fitting calculation, with the components' positions fixed as in the figure, is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=448$). The value of this sum is about 3×10^{-3} .

Comparing the Fig. 4c and the Figs. 14 and 15, we can see that the misfit is larger in these two last cases. Of course, if instead of using a line to represent the data we use a symbol for each datapoint, for instance a circle with a relevant size as in the case of Frank et al., 2012, the visual appearance of the Figs. 14 and 15 can become quite better. In Frank et al., misfits are not given.

Let us consider also a fit using Lorentzian functions, that is we force the value of q-parameters to 2.

Fig.16: The fitting calculation, using Lorentzian functions, is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=448$). The value of this sum is about 6.0×10^{-3} . Let us note that the components' positions are the same as in the Fig.15.

RRUFF allows us to examine the data in the following manner too. We can use the [plot given by the site](#) and look at the data having the high intensity values. Let us consider the possibility (Fig.17) of two “undulations” at 514.3 and 521.3 cm^{-1} to identify the components' centres. The consequent fitting, constrained to these positions, is given in the Fig.18. The misfit that we find has lower values. Another case is given in the Fig.19, with an even lower misfit too.

Fig.17: From the plot courtesy RRUFF, at [link](#), we can evidence two frequencies, here marked in a GNUPLOT rendering of the unpolarized processed data R060277.

Fig. 18: Fitting with two components with centres as in the Fig.17. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=448$). The value of this sum is about 1.2×10^{-3} .

Fig. 19: Maintaining fixed the position of the centre of the second component, that at 521.3 cm^{-1} , and changing the position of the first one, we can find a best fit as in the given plot. The value of the sum of the squares of deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=448$) is about 8.1×10^{-4} .

Without any constrain, the best fit given in the Fig.4c is providing the component (blue) with centre at lower Raman shift as being more relevant than the component (magenta) with centre at larger Raman shift. The opposite is obtained if we use a constrained approach to components' positions.

RRUFF ID R070582 - Let us pass to consider anatase Raman spectrum RRUFF ID 070582 <https://rruff.info/anatase/display=default/R070582>. The Raman data that we will consider are those which have been processed. The following figure show them for an unoriented arrangement, laser 532 nm. The sample is coming from Asker, Akershus, Norway (Source: James Shigley; Owner: RRUFF). "The identification of this mineral has been confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction" (RRUFF).

Fig.20: Processed data of RRUFF ID 070582. On the right, the data with log scale y-axis (semi log scale).

Let us consider the range with the peak at 144 cm^{-1} . The following figure is showing the processed and the raw data, in semi log scale.

Fig. 21: On the left, the processed dat. On the right the raw data as provided by RRUFF.

Fig.22: Decomposition in q -Gaussians of the processed data on Fig.21. Please compare with Fig.2.

In the Fig.22, the decomposition is given with three q -Gaussians, the same we did for the Figure 2. Let us pass to consider the range about 514 cm^{-1} . Also in this case, the processed data are used.

Fig.23: A q -Gaussian fitting onto processed data. Please compare with Fig.4a.

In the Figure 23 we used just one q-Gaussian, to fit onto data. From the discussion given above, we know that two components, with close centers, can exist. Therefore, further fitting must be done. Using two q-Gaussians, the best fit is given in the Fig.24. The positions of the two components are determined by the best fit.

Fig.24: Fitting of two q-Gaussians onto RRUFF 070582 processed data. The sum of the squares of the deviations has been made from $n=1$ to $n=920$. The value of this sum is 1.8×10^{-4} . The positions of the components' centres are determined by the best fit procedure.

Let us consider in detail the values of intensity about the peak, [as in the plot provided by RRUFF](#). We can see, near the peak at 514 cm^{-1} , that two “undulations” at 512 and 517 cm^{-1} seem being visible. Therefore, maintaining fixed the centre of the second component (magenta colour) at 517 cm^{-1} , let us investigate how the fit changes, when positioning the centre of the first component (blue colour) at 511 , 512 , and 513 cm^{-1} . The results given in Fig.25 are congruent to the result given in Fig.24.

Let us stress that in Fig.25, the behaviour of the two q-Gaussians components is determined with the two specific components' central positions established before the fitting procedure. In the case of the left panel of Fig.25, these positions are symmetric about the peak at 514 cm^{-1} , and both at a distance of 3 cm^{-1} . It could be questionable to assume the plot with these two bands as preferable, with respect to the plot in Fig.24, where the sum of the squares of deviations has a lower value. However, in this case (Fig.25 left panel), we have fixed the positions according information from literature (see Ohsaka et al.).

For the two considered samples (RRUFF R060277 and R070582), the fitting with q-Gaussians is giving relevant results. For the case of range about 515 cm^{-1} , and its decomposition in A_{1g} and B_{1g} modes, results are encouraging for further investigations. In any case, the q-Gaussians are giving better results, when compared to Lorentzian and Gaussian functions.

Fig.25: Fitting of two q -Gaussians onto RRUFF 070582 processed data. The positions of the two bands have been fixed at the values given in the corresponding panel, before the fitting procedure. The sum of the squares of the deviations has been made from $n=1$ to $n=920$. The values of this sum are, from left to right, 4.5×10^{-4} , 3.3×10^{-4} and 2.4×10^{-4} , respectively.

RRUFF 2100016 (780nm) – Raman spectrum here considered is available at <https://rruff.info/anatase/display=default/R120064>, East Kemptville Tin mine, East Kemptville, Argyle, Yarmouoth Co., Nova Scotia, Canada (Source: Donald Doell, Owner: RRUFF). “The identification of this mineral has been confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction” (RRUFF). Let us start with data of unoriented sample, at 780 nm laser excitation. The range considered is $469.6 - 565.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Positions of q -Gaussian center (cm^{-1})	Sum of the squares of deviations
510	2.05×10^{-3}
511	7.75×10^{-4}
512	2.21×10^{-3}

Fig.26: Fitting of a q -Gaussian onto RRUFF 120064 (780 nm) processed data. The sum of the squares of the deviations has been made from $n=1$ to $n=800$. The value of this sum is equal to 7.75×10^{-4} , Best position of the component centre at 511 cm^{-1} . The position is the same of the highest intensity datum.

Let us consider two q -Gaussians.

Fig.27: Fitting of two q -Gaussians onto RRUFF 120064 (780 nm) processed data. The sum of the squares of the deviations has been made from $n=1$ to $n=800$. The values of this sum are, from left to right, 5.61×10^{-4} .

RRUFF 2100016 (532nm) – The same sample but excited at 532 nm. The range considered is $469.6 - 565.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig.28: Fitting of a q -Gaussian onto RRUFF 120064 (532 nm) processed data. The sum of the squares of the deviations has been made from $n=1$ to $n=800$. The value of this sum is 1.98×10^{-3} .

Also in this case, we can decompose the profile of the peak with two q -Gaussians.

Fig.29: Fitting of two q -Gaussians onto RRUFF 120064 (532 nm) processed data. The sum of the squares of the deviations has been made from $n=1$ to $n=800$. The values of this sum are, from left to right, 1.69×10^{-4} .

ROD 2100035 – Let us consider the ROD database and the Raman spectrum available at <https://solsa.crystallography.net/rod/cif/2/10/00/2100035.rod> . Related information (date 25 May 2018). The file is available in the Crystallography Open Database (COD), <http://www.crystallography.net/>. The

original data for this entry were provided by IUCr Journals, <http://journals.iucr.org/>. It is told that “file may be used within the scientific community so long as proper attribution is given to the journal article from which the data were obtained.” For the article, see Howard et al., 1991, “Structural and thermal parameters for rutile and anatase”. The Raman measurement device location was the Arizona University. The device was a Thermo Scientific Nicolet Almega XR. Excitation laser wavelength was 780 nm. The direction of polarization is given as unoriented.

In the Fig.30, it is given the Raman spectrum.

Fig. 30: Data of ROD 2100035 unoriented. On the right, the data with log scale y-axis (semi log scale). The semi log scale allows us to identify the ranges already considered for RRUFF samples.

Let us consider again the frequency C, here from 460 to 565 cm^{-1} . Using plot given in the following Fig.31, we can see the data in detail.

Fig. 31: The plot is showing the peak at 511 cm^{-1} . The band is asymmetric, therefore, as we did for the previous samples, we consider two components having their centers at some distance from the peak. For the sake of simplicity, we consider the same distance. In the image, it is shown the case of distance $\pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In the Fig. 31 we can see that the band has its peak at 511 cm^{-1} . Let us try to consider, as we did for the RRUFF sample, two components having their centers at the same distance from the peak (in the Fig.31, the case $\pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is shown). The fitting onto these data is proposed in the Fig.32. In the Table, the sum of the squares of deviations is given.

TABLE

Positions of components' centers (cm^{-1})	Sum of the squares of deviations
511-511	1.25×10^{-3}
510-512	3.34×10^{-4}
509-513	3.06×10^{-4} (best fit)
508-514	4.43×10^{-4}
507-515	5.85×10^{-4}
506-516	1.00×10^{-3}

Fig. 32: Fitting of two q -Gaussians onto ROD 2100035 data. The positions of the two bands have been fixed at the values given in the panels before the fitting procedure. The best fit is given for positions 509 and 513 cm^{-1} .

Results given above are further encouraging investigation on other samples. It seems possible to determine the two components of the band about 515 cm^{-1} .

Remarks

Tsallis q-Gaussians can be easily compared with Gaussian and Lorentzian functions, and with pseudo-Voigtian functions too. In fact, for q-parameter equal to 2, the q-Gaussian is the Lorentzian function, and for q close to 1 the Gaussian function. Therefore, being q-Gaussians the natural generalization of Gaussians and Lorentzians, which are the functions most involved in the Raman spectral analysis, the use of Tsallis Gaussians is suggested.

The semi log scale, that we have used here and in previous works regarding diamond and graphite Raman spectrum analyses, is enhancing the visual rendering of far-wing behaviour; this behaviour is relevant for distinguishing q-Gaussians from other functions. In the previous work regarding diamond spectra, we considered the Tsallis q-Gaussian function compared to Kaniadakis κ -Gaussian function, which is another generalization of the Gaussian function. We have shown that Tsallis Gaussians, Kaniadakis Gaussians and pseudo-Voigt functions are providing slightly different results. It is necessary to know the transfer function of the instrument to determine if it is possible to discriminate the results and decide the preferred function. It is also necessary to consider the manner the data have been processed and the role of the baseline. Without any information regarding processing, the Tsallis Gaussian fitting examples, provided here and previously, show that we can use these functions to substitute pseudo-Voigt and Voigt functions.

In the study of diamond Raman spectra, we noted that the far-wings of Kaniadakis Gaussians, pseudo-Voigt and Voigt functions seem being more “Lorentzian” than those of the Tsallis Gaussians. In the cases here proposed for anatase, and previously for [graphite](#), we can see that the wings are properly described by q-Gaussians, and therefore no further functions have been considered for fitting.

Appendix A

For the bands in the Figures 4c and 5, the two ranges have been fitted independently from each other. If we consider the two ranges together, we find the following fits. We find the same positions of the centres of the q-Gaussians. The magenta q-Gaussian has a different q-parameter (difference is of 6%).

Fig. A1

Fig. A2

Appendix B

Besides the depolarized data, the web page <https://rruff.info/anatase/display=default/R060277> is also providing data with three different directions of polarization of laser relative to fiducial mark: 0 ccw, 45 ccw and 90 ccw. At this [link](#), the data as given in the C range about 517 cm^{-1} .

Fig. B1: RUFF ID R060277 polarized 0 ccw Raman spectrum (red), data processed, range C.

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